

Supplement Material

Non-leaders' View on Effective Leadership in Agile Software Development Teams

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1. Online Supplement

1.1. The Interview Guide

This interview is intended to allow the participant to speak freely about the context of his/her team. Let the participant speak freely about his/her work. Try, from time to time, to interpret what the participant is saying in their own words to check that it is correct.

A. Introduction

- Could you tell us a bit about yourself (your background, experiences, technologies you master, etc)?
 - How long have you been working in the area?
- What is your current position/function in the team?
- How big is your team?
- How long have you been working in the company/project?
- What are your current tasks?
- Do you identify with any gender (female/male/non-binary) or do you prefer not to answer?

B. Examples of follow-up questions on agile methods

- What is your experience with agile methods?
- Which agile method do you use in your team today?
- Could you describe what the agile work process looks like in your team today?
- What would you define as the biggest advantages of agile methods in general?
- Do you have any other aspects that you think we have not covered and that you consider to be an important part of agile working?

C. Examples of follow-up questions on leadership

- Do you see leadership as a function of a particular person or as a property of the team?
 - Can you give an example?
- Is there someone in a leadership role in your team?
- Who would you say is in charge of your team?
- How is the leadership format she/he adopts?
- Does the leader usually distribute leadership activities (decision making, responsibilities) dynamically with the rest of the team?
 - If so, how does this happen in your view?
- Do you believe that the way the leader distributes these responsibilities is balanced among all members or do you notice any differences?
- How do you receive/exercise these leadership activities?
 - Do you have responsibility for a certain "part" of the development process?
- Do you feel free to make decisions, give opinions?
- Does the fact that other team members have more authority to decide certain situations affect the work of the leaders in any way?
- Do you remember any problems that happened in the team regarding the development process?
 - How did the leader act in the face of this problem?
- What are the biggest challenges of leadership in the agile context?
- For you, what would be an effective leadership in an agile context?

D. Finalization.

1.2. Observation Script

A. General

- How do people interact on a daily basis?
- What are the day-to-day events that occur in the team?
- What meetings take place in the team?
- When do they take place?
- Where do they take place?
- Who participates?
- Who speaks?
- What is the content?
- How do people interact on a daily basis?

- What is the team climate like?
- Is there friendship between people?
- How do non-leaders relate to leaders?
- How do leaders relate to non-leaders?
- What is the level of satisfaction of people?
- What is the behavior of people when they are charged? Why are they charged?
- How do people express their satisfaction in the project?
- Are there signs of self-organization (individual or groups)?
- Are there signs of self-management?
- How do men refer to women in the team? And vice-versa?

B. In the course of the meetings

- What is the purpose of the meeting?
- Who conducts the meetings?
- How do people behave during meetings?
- Is the information leveled for everyone?
- Is there submission when leaders speak?
- How do leaders behave when women speak?
 - And when men speak?
- How does communication with the client occur?
- Is there sharing of leadership activities among non-leaders?
 - How does this sharing occur?
 - Are there differences? What are the differences? Where?
- How do non-leaders refer to leaders?
- And the client?
- Is there tension in communication between leaders and other team members?
- When there is a need for project change, how do people behave?
- Do they show excitement or irritation?
- How do non-leaders usually complain about their work?
 - What about leaders?
- What are these indications?
- How do leaders behave in the face of this?
- Do people have autonomy to do the work?
- Is there tension when clients are mentioned in meetings?
- What is my opinion of the meeting overall?
- What else would you like to add from what was observed?

1.3. Concept Maps - Non-Leaders' viewpoint

1.4. Second interviews - Survey for leaders

Team A:

- In the course of the interviews, the team said that leadership is shared mainly with the more experienced developers.
 - How do you see this sharing of your leadership with others?
 - Regarding the experience of this developer, is this related to him/her having more experience in the technologies/tools used, experience in previous projects? Or is it because of the time he/she has been in the project?
- During the meetings, the predominant language for communication is English. Do you believe that the information may not be 100% leveled among everyone due to this language difference?
 - How can this impact on leadership activities, in your opinion?
 - What is your role in the team on the company side?
- Developers with leadership profile are observed for the frequency in which they give opinions, suggestions, for their soft skills related to leadership etc. Sometimes,

in your absence, they are ready to pass on the information and already have a certain period participating in the project. Can you confirm this statement?

- Do less experienced developers need a certain confirmation/permission from you to give their opinion during the meetings?
- In the retrospective meeting, the rotation between developers to conduct the meeting can be seen as an example of sharing leadership activities. Did developers from the university side ever participate?
- During the observation process, a more experienced developer felt the need to do internal retrospectives. He suggested it and did all the organization, communicating it to his colleagues. Did this meeting (internally) continue to happen?
 - With these meetings, what did you observe positive and/or negative in the team?
 - Was there rotation between people to conduct the meeting as well?
- How do you describe yourself as a leader?
- How do you describe your leadership?

Team B:

- In the retrospective meeting observed, you recognized one of the senior developers as one of the system owners, giving him full autonomy to exercise decision-making within the team.
 - How do you see the sharing of your leadership with others?
 - About the experience of this developer, is it related to him having more experience in the technologies/tools used, experience in previous projects?
Or would it be because of the time he/she has been in the project?
- How do you describe yourself as a leader?
- How do you describe your leadership?

1.5. Nomination and refinement of Themes

Non-leaders' view of agile and effective leadership			
Theme	Category	Subcategory	Quote

Situational leadership	Leadership as a function	Leader commands the team	<p><i>"I think it is the leader (who is in the command)." - P5</i></p> <p><i>"It is the leader (who is in the command)" - P1</i></p>
		Acts as a facilitator	<p><i>"He is the coach, he is our facilitator, he also ends up being a shoulder friend at least for our team." - P6</i></p> <p><i>"[The leader] Listening to everyone's opinion, I think that's very important." - P3</i></p> <p><i>"In one-on-ones, which are more managerial, [the leader] always asks about the general mood of the team, asks our opinion about various things." - P2</i></p>
	Distributes leadership according to the experience and availability	According to the experience of the non-leader	<p><i>"Especially when there were problems in the database, because I had experience in this, I was left to decide the pairs, so he [the leader] put me in these stories." - P5</i></p> <p><i>"Only in some moments that maybe some decisions had a very big weight, taking into account the roles within the team (...) like someone being responsible for a very large refactoring and the person being still undergraduate and not having so much experience on this." - P1</i></p>
		Non-leaders take on task-level responsibilities	<p><i>"... When a story was already mine, and it ended up having a link with the database ones.... Then the leader would say: 'oh, talk to him' (...)" - P5</i></p> <p><i>"We also have this opportunity (to manage), but at a more task level." - P1</i></p>

1.6. Observations' Mind Maps

Team A

Chat obs.:
There were no observations in the chat, linked to the meeting, in the observation period

Interesting Points
Because the leader speaks most of the time, directing the team, I felt an air of submission between leader and led. Is this feeling real among developers?

Team B

